

**Punching Holes In The Life Could Have Formed Inside of Cracks in
Rocks Hypothesis**

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*The statements made in this essay represent the opinions of the author.

In the song, “Say Amen,” Howard Hewitt sang the line that “Everything’s not what it seems. There’s a stronger force behind the scenes.” By this Hewitt was referencing the deceptive nature of things that seem concrete and iron clad; contending instead that there is often a hidden element that alludes to God’s presence in the situation. Similarly, in the atheist community, a more recent attempt has been made to declare God nonexistent by presenting the results of an experiment, which to some seem logical and irrefutable. Yet, akin to Hewitt’s statement, there is indeed a stronger force behind the scenes which is revealed in the finer details of this experiment. A critical examination leads back to one conclusion, the truth that God is real and proved circumstantially in the finer details.

A group of researchers concluded that life may have formed in the cracks of volcanoes (Thompson, 2024). Matreux et al (2024) claimed to have arrived at this conclusion because water-filled fractures and thin, connected pathways are found in a variety of geological settings, from mafic to ultramafic rocks in volcanic complexes to geothermal or hydrothermal systems and sedimentary layers. Hence, they set up a synthetic set of systems and attempted to mimic what they believe were the atmospheric conditions on earth prior to any evidence of life. Then, they ran water through the laboratory-created “cracks,” over what mimicked heat fluxes. According to Thompson (2024) “They discovered that the heat flowing across these geologic networks sorted and filtered molecules, helping them create longer chains called [polymers] that are essential for life.”

While the explanation of their results sounds convincing and plausible at first glance, is everything truly what it seems? Based on the following information, the answer is a very obvious no. The sorting and filtering of atoms from their original molecules will happen in some hydrophobic elements regardless of heat source (**See Diagram A**). Additionally, the

extreme temperatures of the hydrothermal fluids and vents would make the formation of polymers plausible (**See Diagram B**). However, the extreme temperatures of the hydrothermal vents disallow the formation and/or usage of uracil, which is critical for RNA function. Furthermore, the presence of methanol in the hydrothermal fluids renders the transition from polymers to RNA molecules impossible. Moreover, the use of hypothetical language demonstrates that these researchers likely lack certainty with respect to the truth of their conclusions. Adding to that, geothermal waters can reach up to 150 degrees Celsius, destroying the integrity of rna permanently. Additionally, abiogenesis or the ability of life to arise from nonlife has been proven impossible. Indicated in these facts is that the researchers conducting this experiment have reached an erroneous conclusion. The premise that life could have formed in volcanic cracks is lacking in accuracy. Thus, the only way for life to form by deduction is from a living source.

Although the scientists conducting this experiment produced some impressive results in terms of polymers and other molecules that were chemically similar to some of the building blocks of life, there is a fundamental flaw in their report. RNA cannot form in the real world hydrothermal fluids. Uracil is a necessary component of RNA that helps carry out the synthesis of many enzymes necessary for cell function (Brody, 2024). Although the laboratory setting was ideal for forming the building blocks of DNA, conditions in the real world hydrothermal fluids differ sharply. This difference eliminates the possibility of life forming this way as uracil is easily broken down at extreme temperatures (Bergman, 2000). Temperatures in real world hydrothermal fluids are at least 350 degrees Celsius (Oceanic Hydrothermal Fluids, 2018). The highest temperature reported in this experiment was 90 degrees Celsius. From this, it can be deduced that under the conditions present in the real world, the uracil would have lost its ability

to carry out its function, if it could form at all; disallowing the formation of RNA. Without RNA, life would not have begun.

Moreover, all RNA hydrogen bases failed to enrich when the experiment was conducted using methanol. In methanol “the accumulation and enrichment are almost entirely suppressed” (Matreux et al, 2024). This is significant because methanol is present in hydrothermal fluids (Hydrothermal Vents, 2015). For this reason, it is clear that the methanol present would have had an inhibitory effect on the formation of RNA. Without RNA, DNA would have failed to materialize. In the absence of DNA, life would not have come to be. This fact demonstrates with certainty the impossibility that life could have formed in the manner proposed by the scientists in this study.

While the previously stated factors represent hydrothermal temperature waters, the other factor for consideration is geothermal waters or waters warmed by heat from within the earth. Geothermal waters can reach temperatures in excess of 150 degrees Celsius (High Temperature, 2024). While the experiment showed maximum heats of 90 degrees Celsius, the upper temperature would have caused irreparable damage to the RNA before it had a chance to form. Additionally, boiling DNA even a little has been shown to damage DNA (Stanford Researchers, 2023). Hence, the experimental model is not indicative of real world conditions as the real world would have included the upper temperatures to view their effects. Logically concluded is that the boiling temperature of geothermal waters would not have allowed for life to start. Hence, life could not have started in this type of environment. This knowledge is likely a reason that temperatures above 90 degrees were not used in this experiment.

Adding substance to the contention that the researchers presented erroneous experimental results is that the authors of this experimental study utilized hypothetical language in their abstract. When analyzing the abstract, the expression “could have” was detected six times. In the majority of scientific studies that I have read, the authors have used language such as a “suggests that,” “demonstrates that,” “alludes to,” and several other expressions that demonstrate a degree of certainty, followed by the claim itself. The use of hypothetical language in the abstract indicates that the researchers likely lack reasonable assuredness that their conclusions are correct. Could it be that they are aware of the uracil factor and its impact on their position? Might they be aware of the inhibitory effects of methanol? This would seem very plausible as the use of hypothetical language would account for any potential flaws in their results without their having to state them directly.

Besides the aforementioned facts, the impossibility of abiogenesis demonstrates with certainty that life could not have occurred in the cracks of volcanic rock. Abiogenesis or the formation of life from inorganic materials posits that for life to exist, there is a lack of necessity for God. Further assumed by proponents of this theory is that life could have formed naturally via inanimate materials through natural processes acting on these materials over time. However, mathematics, which goes hand in hand with science tells us a much different story. For example, the simplest form of life, the amoeba, has approximately 13,000 genes (Wasserman, 2022). Using the model of theoretical probability, which assumes that this is a real possibility. The chance that 10% of these genes could form by random chance is approximately 1 in 10 to the 4,048th power. At 1 in 10 to the 50th power, the event is declared impossible from a statistical standpoint (Omerbasic, 2021). Looking at the total number of genes in an amoeba, the chance is clearly as close to zero as one can get without observing an event. Here, the logical conclusion is

that if life cannot come from inorganic material, life can only come from another source of life. Consequently, we can say with assuredness that there was a living being who created life as we know it.

In light of all these facts, this study proves once again why the only rational explanation for life as we know it is an omnipotent God. For one, the temperatures of the real hydrothermal fluids would have totally destroyed uracil if it could have formed in the first place. However, in this study, the temperatures were significantly reduced, enabling the uracil to remain a stable part of the RNA molecule building blocks. Coupling this with the fact that none of the building blocks were shown to enrich in methanol, which is present in hydrothermal fluids, is a very clear indication that life would fail to materialize under these circumstances due to its inhibitory effects. Also, geothermally heated waters reach in excess of 159 degrees Celsius, which irreparably damages RNA as well as causes DNA damage. Additionally, the use of hypothetical language to present one's findings likely indicates a lack of certainty with respect to the probative nature of these findings. Furthermore, the fact that the chance of a single cell amoeba forming by random chance from inanimate materials is nonexistent, demonstrates that the claims made in this study are an overstatement of what they prove. Instead, being as though abiogenesis is impossible, the sole manner in which life can come to be is through another living source. This proves that God is real and is a spiritual life form whose presence provides the only rational explanation for life as we know it.

Diagram A- Fruit slices in boiling water.

Step 1- Three candy fruit slices were placed in room temperature water.

Step 2- The candy fruit slices were boiled for 5 minutes and observed. During the boiling, the sugar molecules and high fructose corn syrup molecules were observed separating and coming together to form higher concentrations.

Step 3- The boiling was stopped and the activity taking place was observed further. Here, the formation of polymers of sugar and high fructose corn syrup were observed.

Diagram B- The Final Results

The sample was frozen for the purpose of solidifying the observed chemical reactions. It was observed that;

- 1.) The sugar molecules increased in concentration;
- 2.) The high fructose corn syrup increased in concentration;
- 3.) Some polymers of sugar and high fructose corn syrup formed

Conclusion:

Any time hydrophobic elements are subjected to extreme heat, they tend to break apart from their original configurations and “clump up” with atoms/molecules that are the same as they are. They are also capable of forming polymers. This however does not mean that life could form like this as there are a host of other elements needed. Instead, it proves that polymers form and concentrations increase during the chemical change that takes place when thermal energy is applied to molecules.

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